

From Pauli to Dirac via Kronecker and beyond

Adolf Cusmariu
adolcus@gmail.com

1. Review

The Pauli sigma matrices [1]

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

can be used to derive the gamma matrices [2]

$$\gamma_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

in (at least) two ways; as Pauli 'composites'

$$\gamma_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I}_2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbf{I}_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_1 \\ -\sigma_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_2 \\ -\sigma_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_3 \\ -\sigma_3 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

or via Kronecker products:

$$\gamma_0 = \sigma_3 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \quad \gamma_1 = i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_1 \quad \gamma_2 = i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_2 \quad \gamma_3 = i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_3$$

These matrices are obviously traceless; but, while the sigma's are also Hermitian and involutive, only γ_0 is so. γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_3 are skew-Hermitian and skew-involutive. As for commutator relationships, both sigma and gamma matrices anti-commute.

So, how unique is the set of these gamma matrices?

2. Newbies

Apart from the obvious outcome $\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 = \mathbf{I}_4$, Kronecker products offer eleven more sigma pairings, beyond those leading to the gamma foursome; in obvious notation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{g}_{01} &= \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1 & \mathbf{g}_{02} &= i\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2 & \mathbf{g}_{03} &= \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_3 \\ \mathbf{g}_{10} &= \gamma_5 = \sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 & \mathbf{g}_{11} &= \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1 & \mathbf{g}_{12} &= i\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2 & \mathbf{g}_{13} &= \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3 \\ \mathbf{g}_{20} &= i\sigma_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 & \mathbf{g}_{21} &= \gamma_1 = i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_1 & \mathbf{g}_{22} &= \gamma_2 = i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_2 \\ \mathbf{g}_{23} &= \gamma_3 = i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_3 & \mathbf{g}_{30} &= \gamma_0 = \sigma_3 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \\ \mathbf{g}_{31} &= \sigma_3 \otimes \sigma_1 & \mathbf{g}_{32} &= i\sigma_3 \otimes \sigma_2 & \mathbf{g}_{33} &= \sigma_3 \otimes \sigma_3 \end{aligned}$$

These newbie matrices – clearly traceless - are shown below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{01} &= \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & g_{02} &= i\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 g_{03} &= \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} & g_{10} &= \sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 = \gamma_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 g_{11} &= \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & g_{12} &= i\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 g_{13} &= \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & g_{20} &= i\sigma_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 g_{31} &= \sigma_3 \otimes \sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & g_{32} &= i\sigma_3 \otimes \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 g_{33} &= \sigma_3 \otimes \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

Pauli composites are also available here; thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{01} &= \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_1 \end{pmatrix} & g_{02} &= i \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_2 \end{pmatrix} & g_{03} &= \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_3 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_3 \end{pmatrix} & g_{10} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{I}_2 \\ \mathbf{I}_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 g_{11} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & g_{12} &= i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & g_{13} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_3 \\ \sigma_3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & g_{20} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{I}_2 \\ -\mathbf{I}_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 g_{31} &= \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sigma_1 \end{pmatrix} & g_{32} &= i \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sigma_2 \end{pmatrix} & g_{33} &= \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_3 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sigma_3 \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

Do these newbies share any properties with the gamma matrices? The table below has suggestive results.

Matrix	Involution	Hermitian	Eigenvalues
g01	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1
g02	-I ₄	Skew	<i>i,-i, i,-i</i>
g03	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1
g10	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1
g11	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1
g12	-I ₄	Skew	<i>i,-i, i,-i</i>
g13	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1
g20	-I ₄	Skew	<i>i,-i, i,-i</i>
g21= γ_1	-I ₄	Skew	<i>i,-i, i,-i</i>
g22= γ_2	-I ₄	Skew	<i>i,-i, i,-i</i>
g23= γ_3	-I ₄	Skew	<i>i,-i, i,-i</i>
g30= γ_0	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1
g31	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1
g32	-I ₄	Skew	<i>i,-i, i,-i</i>
g33	Y	Y	-1,-1,1,1

3. Commutators

The table above shows that matrix set $S1 = \{g_{02}, g_{12}, g_{20}, g_{32}\}$ shares the anti-Hermitian, anti-involutive, and eigenvalue properties of the matrices $\gamma_1, \gamma_2,$ and $\gamma_3,$ while the set $S2 = \{g_{01}, g_{03}, g_{10}, g_{11}, g_{13}, g_{31}, g_{33}\}$ matches features with $\gamma_0.$ Can a distinct foursome be extracted from these to rival the anti-commutative properties of the gamma set? The table below, painstakingly made using OCTAVE, collates

results; a minus sign among a pairing indicates commutation, while a plus sign implies anti-commutation.

	γ_5							γ_1	γ_2	γ_3	γ_0				
	g01	g02	g03	g10	g11	g12	g13	g20	g21	g22	g23	g30	g31	g32	g33
γ_5	g01														
	+	g02													
	+	+	g03												
	-	-	-	g10											
	-	+	+	-	g11										
	+	-	+	-	+	g12									
	+	+	-	-	+	+	g13								
	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	g20							
γ_1	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	g21						
γ_2	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	g22					
γ_3	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	g23				
γ_0	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	g30			
	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	g31		
	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	g32	
	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	g33

From set **S1** only matrices g_{12} , g_{20} , g_{32} form an anti-commuting set; cells highlighted in yellow. However, no single matrix from set **S2** anti-commutes with all these three. Thus the Dirac foursome is unique, well, almost; matrix $g_{10} = \gamma_5$ also anti-commutes with γ_1 , γ_2 , and γ_3 and matches features with γ_0 , offering a replacement.

4. Connections

Dirac's seminal article [3] derives gamma matrices that are Hermitian, involutive and anti-commutative. The article references Pauli's spin matrices, then uses them as building blocks; however, his book [3a] omits Pauli altogether (p. 257) and offers an independent derivation of the spin matrices (pp. 149-150). A more recent derivation is in [4].

Now, it is instructive to follow Dirac's ingenious, if ad hoc, path; upper-case Greek sigma script is used here to distinguish from Pauli's lower-case sigma usage. First appears the set

$$\Sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Next, this threesome

$$\rho_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \rho_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \rho_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

is introduced; together these generate (upper-case again) Dirac's gamma set as:

$$\Gamma_1 = \rho_2 \Sigma_1 \quad \Gamma_2 = \rho_2 \Sigma_2 \quad \Gamma_3 = \rho_2 \Sigma_3 \quad \Gamma_4 = \rho_3$$

In matrix form these are

$$\Gamma_1 = -i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Gamma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Gamma_3 = -i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Gamma_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

This set is involutive, Hermitian and anti-commutative; the connection with the gamma set γ is now obvious:

$$\Gamma_1 = -i\gamma_1 \quad \Gamma_2 = -i\gamma_2 \quad \Gamma_3 = -i\gamma_3 \quad \Gamma_4 = \gamma_0$$

How did Dirac discover his gamma set? The 1928 article [2] has a recipe. From relativistic invariance considerations he realized the three Pauli matrices are insufficient, in his words '*because then it would not be possible to find a fourth*'. Still, guided by their properties, he first produced the Σ and ρ matrices above by 'stretching' Pauli's set from size 2x2 to 4x4 by ingenious row and column operations; then an interim step produced alpha matrices:

$$\alpha_1 = \rho_1 \Sigma_1 \quad \alpha_2 = \rho_1 \Sigma_2 \quad \alpha_3 = \rho_1 \Sigma_3 \quad \alpha_4 = \rho_3$$

which are still involutive, Hermitian and anti-commutative; finally, replacement of ρ_1 in the alphas with ρ_2 yielded his gamma set.

Is there a more direct path?

The ingenious becomes ingenuous when using Kronecker products and Pauli composition. Dirac's Σ threesome obtained by 'stretching' the σ set is simply

$$\Sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_3 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

or in terms of Kronecker products

$$\Sigma_1 = \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1 \quad \Sigma_2 = \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2 \quad \Sigma_3 = \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_3$$

Similarly, his ρ set is

$$\rho_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{I}_2 \\ \mathbf{I}_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \rho_2 = i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{I}_2 \\ \mathbf{I}_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \rho_3 = \Gamma_4 = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I}_2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbf{I}_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

or what is the same

$$\rho_1 = \sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \quad \rho_2 = \sigma_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \quad \rho_3 = \sigma_3 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2$$

Incidentally, the ρ matrix set is really Pauli's σ set in disguise; just change \mathbf{I}_2 to $\mathbf{1}$ in the Pauli composite format above. Also, ρ_1 is the 'fifth' gamma matrix γ_5 .

Next, the mixed-product property for Kronecker products [5] helps close the loop neatly; thus

$$\alpha_1 = \rho_1 \Sigma_1 = (\sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2)(\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1) = \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1$$

$$\alpha_2 = \rho_1 \Sigma_2 = (\sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2)(\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2) = \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2$$

$$\alpha_3 = \rho_1 \Sigma_3 = (\sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2)(\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_3) = \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3$$

$$\alpha_1 = \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1 \quad \alpha_2 = \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2 \quad \alpha_3 = \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3 \quad \alpha_4 = \rho_3$$

Finally, from

$$\Gamma_1 = \rho_2 \Sigma_1 = (\sigma_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2)(\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1) = \sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_1$$

$$\Gamma_2 = \rho_2 \Sigma_2 = (\sigma_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2)(\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2) = \sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_2$$

$$\Gamma_3 = \rho_2 \Sigma_3 = (\sigma_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2)(\mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_3) = \sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_3$$

Thus Dirac's gamma set follows algebraically from Pauli's sigma set:

$$\Gamma_1 = \sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_1 \quad \Gamma_2 = \sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_2 \quad \Gamma_3 = \sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_3 \quad \Gamma_4 = \sigma_3 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2$$

References

[1] W. Pauli: 'Wave Mechanics' – Pauli Lectures on Physics, Vol. 5, Dover Publications (2000), Sec. 33.

[2] Wikipedia article on 'Gamma Matrices'

[3] P. A. M. Dirac, 'The Quantum Theory of the Electron', Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Vol. 117, No. 778 (1928), pp. 610-624.

[3a] P. A. M. Dirac: 'The Principles of Quantum Mechanics', 4th Edition, (1958) Oxford Clarendon Press.

[4] A. Cusmariu, 'Whence Pauli matrices?', <https://www.zenodo.org/record/7979146>

[5] Wikipedia article on 'Kronecker products'